

Brown plant hopper management by exploiting the host plant resistance in rice

Arun Chacko^{1*}, Jayalekshmy V. G²., and Shahiba A. M¹

¹*PhD Scholar, Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, College of Agriculture,
Vellayani, Trivandrum, Kerala*

²*Professor and Head, Department of Seed Science and Technology, College of Agriculture,
Vellayani, Trivandrum, Kerala*

corresponding author: arun7joseph@gmail.com

Brown Plant Hopper (BPH), *Nilaparvata lugens* (Homoptera: Delphacidae), is one of the most devastating pests, causing significant yield loss in the majority of Asian rice cultivars. BPH is managed through a variety of pest management strategies, including the use of chemicals, improved agricultural practices, and the development of resistant cultivars. To combat BPH outbreaks, however, employing an excessive amount of pesticides is harmful to human health, expensive from a financial perspective, and harmful to the ecosystem and biodiversity. The most dependable, accurate, cost-effective, and ecologically safe course of action for BPH treatment is to develop a long-lasting host-plant resistance mechanism. Quick adaptation and evolution of BPH is a serious concern that can be addressed by developing broad-spectrum resistance by the introgression of genes imparting resistance to BPH. However, advances in molecular marker technology along with cutting-edge science of genomics such as high-throughput genotyping, next generation sequencing and phenotyping helps in assisting a breeder to widely explore the diverse germplasm, identification and easy transfer of genes/QTLs conferring resistance and development of varieties with multiple resistance thus exploiting host-plant resistance mechanisms for insect pest management in rice. For sustainable management of insect pests in rice, host plant resistance mechanism sounds as an economical, efficient, durable and environmentally safe strategy.

Keywords: *Brown plant hopper, host-plant resistance, gene pyramiding, pest management*